

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**FREQUENCY OF IN-HOSPITAL MORTALITY IN PATIENTS
WITH HIGH NEUTROPHIL/LYMPHOCYTE RATIO AS
MARKER OF DISEASE ACTIVITY IN ANKYLOSING
SPONDYLITIS**Dr Saqiba Khan¹, Dr Abdul Ghaffar Khan², Dr Muhammad Usama Hassan³¹Services Institute of Medical Sciences, Lahore

Article Received: May 2020

Accepted: June 2020

Published: July 2020

Abstract:

Introduction: Ankylosing spondylitis (AS) is a systemic chronic inflammatory condition involving mainly sacroiliac joint and spine. **Objectives:** The purpose of this study is to find the frequency of in-hospital mortality in patients with high neutrophil/lymphocyte ratio as marker of disease activity in ankylosing spondylitis. **Material and methods:** This cross-sectional study was conducted in SIMS, Lahore during March 2019 to January 2020. All patient who have ankylosing spondylitis will be assessed and those who fulfill the inclusion criteria will be included in study group. All patients will be assessed using BASDAI and BASFI for disease activity. **Results:** The patient group consisted of 35 patients (26 men (74.3%) and 9 women (25.7%)), and the control group consisted of 38 healthy volunteers (26 men (68.4%) and 12 women (31.6%)). Mean age of the patients and healthy controls was 38.9 ± 11.9 and 37.3 ± 6.9 , respectively. A total of 27 patients had HLA-B27 analysis; 15 (68.2%) of them were found to be positive. Four (12.9%) patients had a history of uveitis. Thirteen (46.4%) patients had enthesitis, and 14 (43.8%) patients had peripheral arthritis. **Conclusion:** It is concluded that neutrophil lymphocyte ratio can be a valuable and reliable tool of disease activity in mortality of in-hospital patients who have started anti-tumor necrosis factor (TNF) drugs for AS.

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Please cite this article in press Saqiba Khan et al, *Frequency Of In-Hospital Mortality In Patients With High Neutrophil/Lymphocyte Ratio As Marker Of Disease Activity In Ankylosing Spondylitis.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(07).

INTRODUCTION:

Ankylosing spondylitis (AS) is a systemic chronic inflammatory condition involving mainly sacroiliac joint and spine. It represents the prototype of spondyloarthropathies. Its etiology is unknown but is associated with HLA B27 in 90 to 95 % cases. Worldwide prevalence of AS is about 0.5 to 1 % while that in northern and southern Pakistan is 0.1 to 0.9/1000 population [1].

AS can be diagnosed clinically and radiographically using modified New York diagnostic criteria. There is no specific diagnostic test. Clinically disease activity can be assessed using Bath Ankylosing spondylitis disease activity score, Bath Ankylosing spondylitis Functional index and ASAS (ASDAI scores). ESR and others acute phase reactants are markers of inflammation and are usually tested in AS patients. ESR and other acute phase reactant are not related to disease activity and ESR changes are seen in <50% case of AS patients [2]. IL 6 and TNFs are considered markers of inflammation and disease activity in AS patients.

Full blood count including Total leukocyte count and platelets are routine investigations for Rheumatological diseases. The circulating white blood cell (WBC) undergoes relative changes in systemic inflammation, typically represented by lymphopenia and neutrophilia. WBC and subtype counts have been identified as biomarkers of inflammation, neutrophil/ lymphocyte ratio (NLR) is a marker of subclinical inflammation and has been used in combination with other inflammatory markers to determine inflammation in both auto- and non-autoimmune diseases. Raised NLR has high sensitivity and specificity for acute appendicitis [3,4].

NLR and PLR are indicator of disease activity in SLE patients. NLR is increased in in lupus nephritis. Raised NLR and PLR are indicator of active RA. NLR and PLR are indicator of inflammations and disease activity in SLE, rheumatoid arthritis and others inflammatory conditions [5].

Objectives

The purpose of this study is to find the frequency of in-hospital mortality in patients with high neutrophil/lymphocyte ratio as marker of disease activity in ankylosing spondylitis.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted in SIMS, Lahore during March 2019 to January 2020. All patient who have ankylosing spondylitis will be assessed and those who fulfill the inclusion criteria will be included in study group. All patients will be assessed using BASDAI and BASFI for disease activity. Control group will be selected from age and gender matched healthy population. 35 patients will be taken in disease group. Fresh full blood count with ESR will be done from PIMs Hospital laboratory and ratio of neutrophil to lymphocyte and Platelet Lymphocyte will be calculated and entered to a predesigned proforma. Bath ankylosing spondylitis disease activity index was used to evaluate waist and hip pain, level and duration of peripheral arthritis and enthesitis, and morning stiffness. Total blood count evaluation was performed with impedance, optic laser scatter, and radio frequency method. ESR (mm/hour) was measured with photometric capillary flow kinetic analysis, and CRP (mg/dL) was measured with immune-turbidimetric assay. NLR was found with a mathematical calculation of the ratio of neutrophils with lymphocytes.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were performed with SPSS statistical package, version 19.0 (Inc, Chicago, IL, USA). The data are given as mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS:

The patient group consisted of 35 patient (26 men (74.3%) and 9 women (25.7%)), and the control group consisted of 38 healthy volunteers (26 men (68.4%) and 12 women (31.6%)). Mean age of the patients and healthy controls was 38.9 ± 11.9 and 37.3 ± 6.9 , respectively. A total of 27 patients had HLA-B27 analysis; 15 (68.2%) of them were found to be positive. Four (12.9%) patients had a history of uveitis. Thirteen (46.4%) patients had enthesitis, and 14 (43.8%) patients had peripheral arthritis.

Table 01: Pre- and post-treatment laboratory values of patients

	Pre-treatment	Treatment 3 month ahead	p value
Leukocyte ($\times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$)	10.330 \pm 2.66	8.019 \pm 2.004	
Neutrophil ($\times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$)	6.596 \pm 2.11	4.693 \pm 1.399	
Lymphocyte ($\times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$)	2.771 \pm 1.15	2.783 \pm 7.26	
Hemoglobin	12.82 \pm 1.62	13.73 \pm 1.55	
Platelet ($\times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$)	360.37 \pm 113.77	279.42 \pm 87.44	
NLR	2.67 \pm 1.17	1.80 \pm 0.79	<0.001
MCV	81.80 \pm 7.31	82.86 \pm 7.91	<0.001
RDW	16.08 \pm 2.38	15.78 \pm 2.17	<0.001
MPV	8.80 \pm 1.69	8.84 \pm 1.50	0.004
4+9	39.97 \pm 36.05	14.02 \pm 24.08	<0.001
CRP (mg/dL)	2.57 \pm 3.09	1.28 \pm 2.08	0.007
BASDAI	6.57 \pm 0.93	4.22 \pm 0.83	<0.001

DISCUSSION:

Bath ankylosing spondylitis disease activity index scores, ESR, and CRP are the common measures for determining the disease activity and patients' response to the treatment. In this study, we found that NLR correlated with these parameters. To best of our knowledge, this is the first study showing the relation between NLR and disease activity in patients with AS [6].

TNF-alpha plays a major role in the pathogenesis of AS. The net effect of TNF-alpha on neutrophils is not clear; however, it has effects on interleukin (IL)-1, IL-6, IL-8, and granulocyte macrophage colony-stimulating factor. Also, it is an essential element in hematopoietic progenitor cell differentiation and maturation [7].

The relation between higher levels of NLR and systemic inflammation is not clear yet. Systemic inflammation has deleterious effects on vascular endothelial cells through decreased production of nitric oxide and prostacyclin, which causes decreased vasodilation and anti-thrombosis [8]. Also, stimulated leukocytes have increased adherence to the vascular endothelium. Cytokines, like IL-1ra, IL-6, IL-7, IL-8, IL-12, and PDGF, play a considerable role in inflammation and may have an effect on increased NLR[9].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that neutrophil lymphocyte ratio can be a valuable and reliable tool of disease activity in mortality of in-hospital patients who have started anti-tumor necrosis factor (TNF) drugs for AS. Further studies with larger patient groups, longer follow-up duration, and radiographic end-points are required to verify our findings concerning the role of NLR in the inflammatory process of rheumatologic diseases.

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